

Synthesis of steroidal enamine – pyrrolidine derivative

Shamsuzzaman*, Nazish Siddiqui and Tabassum Siddiqui

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, India

Manuscript received 4 December 2003, revised 27 May 2004, accepted 11 June 2004

Synthesis of steroidal enamine-pyrrolidine derivative (3) from 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one (1) and 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one (2) using pyrrolidine is described.

Pyrrolidine derivatives of different compounds have been synthesized for wide range of industrial, pharmaceutical and biological purposes. Literature reveals that compounds containing pyrrolidine moiety are biologically significant molecules. They have been used for the treatment of vision and memory disorders¹, nerve and mental disorder², inhibiting bone loss³ and for treatment and prevention of circulatory diseases and psychosis⁴. Besides this pyrrolidine derivatives are prepared as dopamine D₁ agonists⁵ and T-lymphocyte suppressant⁶. Some pyrrolidine derivatives have found to be useful as antihypertensive⁷.

In view of these findings we report here in, the synthesis of steroidal enamine-pyrrolidine derivatives, which are expected to possess pharmacological activities. Synthetically also these compounds are very stable because of the presence of conjugated double bonds, these double bonds can provide a site of further conjugate addition. We have utilized derivatives of easily available cholesterol molecule for this purpose and prepared 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one⁸ (1) and 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one⁹ (2) according to the reported procedure and used them as starting material here.

Results and discussion

In the present work 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one (1) and 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one (2) were converted to steroidal enamine-pyrrolidine derivative (3) as in Scheme 1. The authenticity of the product 3 was confirmed by the physical, analytical and spectroscopic methods.

The expected products with acetate and chloro moieties intact at C-3 were not obtained, which was confirmed by the absence of a three proton singlet for -OCOCH₃ around δ 2.1, and a one proton multiplet around δ 4.7–4.9 due to C3 α -H in ¹H NMR spectrum of the product obtained from compound 1. The product obtained from compound 2 gave negative Beilstein test and the absence of one-proton multiplet due to C3 α -H around δ 4.0–4.2 in its ¹H NMR spectrum, further confirmed the absence of chlorine.

Scheme 1

The presence of peaks at δ 6.15–6.21 due to olefinic protons of C2, C3, C4 and the UV spectral data confirmed the presence of extended conjugation [UV λ_{max} (obs.) = 301 nm, UV λ_{max} (calcd.) = 303 nm] in both the products obtained from compound 1 and 2. The products from compound 1 and 2 were found to have the same melting point 110°, and the study of their physical, analytical and spectral data (mixed m.p., elemental analysis, UV, IR, ¹H NMR) revealed the formation of only one product 3 from compound 1 as well as from compound 2. The formation of product 3 is rationalized on the basis of the proposed mechanism (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

^1H NMR spectra were recorded on 300 MHz instrument using TMS as an internal standard (chemical shifts in δ , ppm), IR spectra (KBr) (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) and UV spectra in chloroform were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1800 FTIR. The purity of the compound was established by TLC and by elemental analysis (C, H, N).

Steroidal enamine-pyrrolidine derivative (3) : Freshly distilled pyrrolidine (1.5 ml) was added to a refluxing solution of 3 β -acetoxy cholest-5-en-7-one (**1**) (0.0024 mol) in methanol (10 ml). Refluxing was further continued for 1.5 h, progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction the solution was concentrated to induce crystallization. The crystalline material was filtered, washed with methanol and dried to afford **3** in 71.4% yield, m.p. 110° (Found : C, 85.48; H, 11.32; N, 3.20. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{49}\text{N}$: C, 85.45; H, 11.34; N, 3.21%); UV 301 (3.26); ν_{max} 1658 (C=C), 1384 cm^{-1} (C-N); ^1H NMR, δ 6.15–6.21 (olefinic protons, C2, C3, C4), 5.30 (1H, s, C6-H), 2.28 (8H, m, methylenes of pyrrolidino function), 1.2–1.8 (methylene and methine protons of steroidal skeleton), 1.15 (3H, s, C10-CH₃), 0.90, 0.82 (other steroidal methyl protons), 0.73 (3H, s, C13-CH₃).

Under similar reaction conditions 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one (**2**) gave the same product **3** with similar physical, analytical and spectral characteristics with 68.2% yield, in 3 h.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Chairman, Department of Chemistry for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. D. T. Ross, H. Sauer, G. S. Hamilton and J. P. Steiner, *Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **132**, 166513.
2. S. Murakami, T. Ikebe, Y. Morimoto and S. Takehara, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, **116**, 235427.
3. H. U. Bryant and T. A. Grese, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **123**, 988.
4. K. Fujimoto, N. Tanaka, F. Asai, T. Ito and H. Koike, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **123**, 9288.
5. T. Hoshiko, K. Sato, S. Suda, H. Oinuma, N. Yoneda, K. Myake, N. Minami, T. Matsuoka and H. Ishihara, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1995, **123**, 169495.
6. R. D. Connell, D. G. Osterman, M. E. Katz and R. D. Dally, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1994, **121**, 230670.
7. G. Lavielle, M. Laubie and F. Colpaert, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1992, **116**, 128683.
8. W. G. Dauben and G. J. Fonken, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4736.
9. A. H. Milburn and E. V. Truter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1736.